

THE ROLE OF COLLABORATIVE TELEGRAM-BASED INSTRUCTION IN THE ENHANCEMENT OF PRAGMATIC COMPETENCE IN IRAQI EFL UNIVERSITY CONTEXT

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Abstract:

This paper addresses the role of collaborative instruction using a Telegram social media application on the enhancement of pragmatic competence of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) in Iraqi university context. A quasi-experimental study with a non-equivalent control group and a pre-test/post-test design has been adopted to find any substantial differences between the two groupings. The first group (N=45) was instructed using 5 to 10 minutes of pragmatics-based video tasks and materials from the Telegram group activities of the group members. At the same time, the second group (N=45) was instructed similarly implementing individual Telegram activities. Findings indicated that teaching pragmatics deploying a virtual classroom instruction model through the Telegram group is found to be more effective than the individual one. The results suggest that teaching pragmatics using a virtual classroom and technology through collaborative Telegram learning activities can serve as one of the appropriate alternatives to advance EFL learners' practical competence.

Key Words: Virtual Classroom; Technology; Collaborative Instruction; Telegram; Pragmatic Competence

1. Introduction:

With the emergence of technological networks in the 2000s, the technologies built upon Web 2.0 platforms that are known as social media, took a variety of kinds such as blogs, wikis, social networking services, and media technologies. Social media has unquestionably impinged into human exchanges a lot since they have significantly altered people's communicative habits (Reinhardt, 2019). Technology (or sometimes called electronic) devices and various applications such as Telegram, Moodle, Google classroom, WhatsApp, and e-mail have lately been increasingly recognized as crucial elements in the process of language teaching and learning (Lankshear & Knobel, 2006; Warschauer & Grimes, 2007). Recently, educational institutions such as schools and universities have admitted the significance and positive effects of modern technologies since they are viewed as complementary instruments to assist the abilities of educators and learners' motivation towards their competences and métier (Chik & Ho, 2017). According to Rostami and Khodabandeh (2019), these developments in technology "resulted in intercultural and socio-pragmatic developments, raised people's awareness of social issues, and shaped language learners' identities" (p.70).

For example, with their specialized features, WhatsApp, Telegram, and email are found to have a positive effect on the enhancement of students' achievement in the skill of writing (AbdAlfattah, 2015; Alfaki & Alharthy, 2014). Therefore, utilizing technology has become a crucial demand in most EFL classes in different countries. Different computer-based tools and instruments have been adopted or adapted in the process of teaching and learning foreign languages. This phenomenon also occurs in both EFL and ESL teaching contexts. Social media has become one of these facilities that support both teachers and learners in what is called 'flipped classroom' or virtual learning environment (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2018; Arifani, 2019; Suranakkharin, 2017). According to Motteram (2013) and Zhu & Chen (2015), various technological aids have been suggested in such environments such as Email, Youtube, Skype, WhatsApp, Videotapes, Data-show presentations, wikis and the like. However, most contexts have limited proficiency in EFL rather than communicative or pragmatic competency. Thus, very few studies have tackled the impact of technologies on the enhancement of learners' pragmatic competence. More specifically, social media such as Telegram and WhatsApp have been rarely focused on, especially as far as the Iraqi academic EFL circle is concerned. For instance, computer-mediated communication (CMC) in its classical form has been the focus of study about pragmatics. Khoshshima, Toroujeni & Samani (2017) argue that this technology would possibly support learners' interlanguage pragmatics. In a previous study, Sykes (2005) attempted to scrutinize the possible link between CMC and Interlanguage Pragmatics and examined the connection between three types of synchronous group discussion (written chat, oral chat, and traditional face-to-face discussion) on how EFL learners of Spanish whose mother tongue was American English acquired the speech act of refusing the invitation. In Sykes' study, "the subjects were assigned to different synchronous group discussions and assess the effect of the modes of discussion using role-play".

In another study, Muzhir, Raheem & Ghani (2013) dealt with the role of videoconferencing (VC) in the development of pragmatic competence in the Iraqi EF1 context. Utilizing a Discourse Completion Test (DCT), it is remarkably concluded that VC learners proved more pragmatically competent than other learners and that VC is a very useful tool of teaching pragmatic competence in EF1 contexts. In another context, Nobre (2018) highlights the significance of technologies in language learning environments because they enhance flexibility in learning, develop interactive strategies in students, motivate online connections and reinforce continuous follow-up and feedback (see Sharikhani, 2014; Kabooha & Elyas 2018). Similarly, it is proposed that e-learning could help students be self-confident since such communicative and technological tools, especially those involving videos require self-management and control. As Sales (2013) discloses, "this type of flipped class encourages students to take responsibility for their learning process when watching videos to organize this process all by themselves". It can be also emphasized that technology can motivate and improve student-centered learning theories (Khoshshima, Toroujeni, & Samani, 2017). Thus, such tools will encourage self-assessment, autonomous learning, and peer-evaluation with ease and benefit.

Arifani (2019) indicates that virtual classes are very effective, as shown by the monitoring process of collaboration between EF1 learners, whose scores were noted to be higher than the ones reached by students receiving individual instruction. However, "the principal aspect of collaboration remains invisible, especially during the out-of-class activity that cannot be optimally monitored. Moreover, the chat history is not indicated, either" (Arifani et al, 2020: 123). Hence, the current study is an attempt to investigate whether a virtual classroom model involving small grouping via Telegram used for interactive activities in small collaborative groups could develop EF1 learners' pragmatic competence more effectively than individual group activities.

2. Literature Review:

2.1. Pragmatic Competence:

Although the term "communicative competence" was introduced by Hymes in the 1960's (Hymes, 1964), communicative and social competences were not under the spot of language teaching and learning until the 1970's (Krisnawati, 2011, p. 105). Defining pragmatics is the key to understanding the meaning of pragmatic competence. Pragmatics is generally defined by different scholars in different ways; for example, it is viewed as the study of language in use or language in context (Levinson, 1983; Kasper, 2001). Additionally, pragmatics is divided into two basic types: the first is linguistic pragmatics in which the focus of the study is on direct and indirect strategies of communication, and then socio-pragmatics which deals with how aspects or notions such as social power, distance, solidarity, rank, and accommodation are related to daily communication in a variety of socio-cultural contexts" (Leech, 1990). Types of competence vary along with the different levels of linguistic apparatus in language. Canale and Swain (1980) classify communicative competence into four kinds: grammatical competence (which involves the speaker's knowledge of syntax, morphology, phonology, and semantics), sociolinguistic competence (which deals with the speaker's perception of appropriate language use), discourse competence (which involves the achievement of cohesion and coherence in spoken and written texts), and strategic competence (which involves the communicative steps used by speakers to make communication more felicitous or upbeat). Similarly, Chomsky (1980) defines pragmatic competence as the speaker's knowledge of the conditions and manners of the appropriate use of language. Afterward, Canale (1988), followed by Bachman (1990) subdivides pragmatic competence into sociolinguistic competence and illocutionary competence which is concerned with the speaker's knowledge of the achievement of different kinds of speech acts (Byram, 1995). On the other hand, Biały (1993) considers discourse competence as a sub-kind of pragmatic competence since "he thinks that pragmatic ability must contain rules with which parts of texts come together to create a coherent discourse".

Consequently, appropriateness is the basic aspect of the achievement of pragmatic competence, and it is the best way of improving the second language (S1) learning (Meier, 1992). Pragmatic competence relies on the activation of socio-cultural norms. Such norms are learned by S1 learners at an advanced level of competence in S1 (Marowa-Hopkins & Strambi, 2005, p. 49). Schmidt (1993) proposes that there is no inherent relationship between the capacity of pragmatic competence and the acquisition of grammatical competence. This demonstrates that pragmatic knowledge can be a prerequisite for successful communication, rather than grammar. Moreover, one can say that teaching pragmatic competence and strategies does not fully depend on grammar teaching. Therefore, pragmatic failure is seen as more influential than a structural one; Amaya (2008, p.12) argues that "pragmatic failures affect the interpretation of messages and sometimes block communication completely".

2.2. Telegram as a Virtual Classroom:

Hamdan, McKnight, McKnight, Arfstrom (2013), and Suranakkharin (2017) emphasized the role of virtual classrooms in the enhancement of collaborative teaching and learning since it reinforces group discussion, daily activity, face-to-face communication among teachers and students. This is on the one hand among students, but on the other hand, it's different in contexts and for different academic aims and objectives. Such technology is supposed to improve or aid collaborative learning in pragmatic competence contexts. As

proposed by Muslem, Mustafa, Usman & Rahman (2017), collaborative learning plays a crucial role in building the quality of learning that all learners deserve and gives them equal opportunities to acquire it. Collaborative learning can be defined as a set of teaching and learning strategies promoting student collaboration in different academic contexts (Arifani, 2019). It motivates the learners' inclination towards self and group evaluation, assessment, confidence, and interaction. However, few studies have dealt with the importance of Telegram in EF1 contexts (Rostami and Khodabandeh, 2018). In their study, they focused on the stylistic differences between Telegram and email writing forms as far as students' activities were concerned." Therefore, more studies are needed to advance our understanding of such virtual technological social media applications in the process of teaching and learning".

3. The Present Study:

3.1. Research Question:

Since this study is intended to measure the effects of utilizing Telegram as a technology for collaborative learning to enhance pragmatic competence in Iraqi EF1 university context, the following question is postured: Will there be any significant difference in the ability of EF1 learners' pragmatic competence after the implementation of collaborative activities in Telegram as a virtual classroom?

3.2. Design of Study:

Arifani et al.'s (2019) model will be used here with some modifications to suit pragmatic goals. This quasi-experimental design is classified as quantitative, involving a non-equivalent control group and pre-test/post-test design. This study aims to find any significant difference in terms of mastery of pragmatic strategies between individual and collaborative Telegram groups. Two different quasi-designs were classified. The first cohort was categorized as a collaborative group. Each collaborative group was assigned collaborative pragmatic activities in their virtual classroom in Telegram. Each group consisted of 8 to 9 learners. The second one was attributed to their activities in an individual group. Each learner was assigned individual pragmatic activities in his or her Telegram. The instructional design for both groups is presented in Table 1 below.

3.3. Participants:

The population consists of three classes of undergraduate students. Two of the classes had been randomly selected as a sample of the study. To find the two homogeneous classes, the researchers had assessed the English scores reached by the learners using an English placement test designed by the Faculty. Thus, two classes were randomly selected and then divided into two groups. The first group of respondents, designated as "Collaborative group", was divided into sub-groups, and each group included 8 to 9 learners with a total of 45 respondent students (22 male, 23 female). However, the second group, designated as "Individual group", consists of 45 students (20 males, 25 females) who were assigned to install Telegram in their smartphones. The first and second groups were attributed to pragmatic activities as collaborative and individual activities in Telegram, respectively. Two tests, namely the pre-and post-test, were administered in the study. The researchers prepared a written pragmatics test for the pre-test and post-test (see Appendix). During the pre-test and the post-test activities, the learners' achievement scores were measured. The elements of pragmatics that were assessed involved speech acts, politeness strategies, implicature, deictic expressions, and presupposition. To address the issue of validity and reliability of research findings, the researchers evaluated the students' portfolio and examined their pragmatic competence development. Cohen's Kappa statistical analysis was implemented to measure inter-rater reliability. This ranged from -0.1 to + 1.0.

Subsequently, the collected data were evaluated and subdivided into three phases. In the first phase, the researchers adopted the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test to establish the normality of the data distribution; then, a homogeneity test was deployed to determine the variance occurring in the data under scrutiny. In the second phase, the researchers measured the average score. The pre-test and post-test findings from both selected groups were analyzed to obtain the average score in each writing test. In the third step, a hypothesis test was performed utilizing a t-test.

Table 1: Summary of teaching pragmatics through Telegram

Stage	Collaborative group activities in Telegram		Individual group activities in Telegram
Stage 1: Introduction	1	Students are assigned to create Telegram groups consisting of 8 to 9 students in each group	Each student is assigned to create an individual Telegram.
	2	Pre-test for both groups	
		5 to 10 minutes of pragmatics-themed videos are prepared for each group.	5 to 10 minutes of pragmatics-themed videos are prepared for each student.
Stage 2: Learning Materials	They deal with:		
	Speech acts, Politeness strategies; Implicature; Deictic expressions; Presupposition		
	1. Outside Class		1. Outside Class

	(a) Each week the instructor sends a conversation video to the students' Telegram groups.	(a) Each week, the instructor sends a conversation video to each student's Telegram.
	(b) Discuss the pragmatic strategies video from their Telegram group.	(b) Each week, every student watches and studies the video individually.
	(c) Each collaborative group watches and discusses notions or a strategy of pragmatic topics from their Telegram group.	(c) Every student learns about the concept of each notion or a strategy of pragmatic topics individually.
	(d) Each week every group completes 10 items of pragmatics exercises.	(d) Each week, every student completes 10 items of pragmatics exercise.
	(e) Submit the exercise to the instructor's Telegram each week.	(e) Each student submits the exercise to the instructor's Telegram individually.
Stage 3: Telegram implementation (week 1 to 6)	2. In Class (60 minutes)	2. In Class (60 minutes)
	(a) Every week the collaborative group holds a classroom discussion and makes a presentation to clarify the pragmatic notions and their related exercises.	(a) Every week, a classroom discussion and an individual presentation are implemented to clarify the pragmatic notions and their related exercises. A random individual presentation selection is appointed.
	(b) The instructor provides feedback and comments.	(b) The instructor provides feedback and comments
Stage 4: week7	Post-test	Post-test

3.4. Results:

The results of normality and homogeneity of collaborative groups and individuals were statistically calculated as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Normality tests between the two groups

Group	Kolmogorov-Smirnov *			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Collaborative Group (CG)	0.20	45	0.331	0.972	45	0.345
Individual Group (IG)	0.17	45	0.480	0.981	45	0.678

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 2 reveals the results of the normality test derived from the collaborative and individual groups. Since the results of the normality test derived from the two groups are beyond Alpha 5% with $p = 0.331$ and $p = 0.480$, the data from both collaborative group and individual group groups have been normally distributed. The results of the homogeneity test derived from the collaborative group and individual group groups using the Levene test indicate that the statistical computation amount was 2.641. The p-value from the test was 0.107 at a 95% confidence level. Since the result of the p-value is bigger than the alpha level (5%), the data are convincingly homogeneous.

Table 3: Mean score comparison between the two groups

Group	N	Mean ± std		
		Pre-test	Post-test	Change
Collaborative Group	45	43.08 ± 7.69	64.25 ± 9.71	21.17
Individual Group	45	39.15 ± 9.05	52.76 ± 11.30	13.61
Difference		3.93	11.49	+ 7.56

As shown in Table 3, the results of the pre-test and post-test mean score comparison between the collaborative group and individual groups are presented. It was found that the learners from the collaborative group reached a mean score of 43.08 in the pre-test with standard deviation (std) = 7.69 and the mean score of the post-test was 64.25 with std = 9.71. Conversely, the learners who were taught in the individual group

mode1 reached a mean score of 39.15 with std = 9.05, and their mean score in the post-test amounted to 52.76 with std = 11.30. It is clear that collaborative activities in Telegram lead to increasing the score of the students by 7.56.

Table 4: Comparison of mean score between groups

Pragmatic Elements	Collaborative Group			Individual Group		
	Pre-test	Post-test	Difference	Pre-test	Post-test	Difference
Speech acts	2.1	3.48	1.38	1.67	2.41	0.74
Politeness strategies	2.32	3.61	1.29	1.88	2.61	0.73
Implicature	2.49	3.31	0.82	2.21	2.68	0.47
Deictic expressions	2.34	3.6	1.26	1.57	2.91	1.34
Presupposition	1.6	2.82	1.22	1.26	1.43	0.17
Total score	10.85	16.82	5.97	8.59	12.04	3.45

Table 4 illustrates the mean scores of learners who were taught in the Collaborative Group (16.82) with a mean change score (5.97) that was higher than the mean scores of those learners who were taught in the Individual Group's (12.04) with a mean change score (3.45) in overall elements of pragmatics obtained namely speech acts, politeness strategies, implicature, deictic expressions, and presupposition. It could be said that both collaborative and individual groups' pragmatic score gains increased from the pre-and post-test. Although both collaborative and individual groups attained their positive score improvement, the score gain of the collaborative group was higher than those individual ones. This may serve to illustrate that the EFL learners' mastery of pragmatic strategies could be fostered by implementing a collaborative Telegram group (consisting of 8 to 9 learners) activities.

More specifically, the finding for the collaborative group indicates that out of all five pragmatic strategies and notions, the speech act strategies proved to be the most familiar for the learners. This is why their speech act score reveals the highest score gain (1.38) among the other pragmatic strategies. In the meantime, learners' scores gained in the category of Implicature are the lowest among the other pragmatic strategies (0.82). "This indicates that Implicature was the most problematic topic for them to grasp. It could be asserted that the collaborative Telegram group significantly contributes to the score improvement of the English speech act and politeness strategies categories in developing pragmatic competence". On the other hand, the results of the individual group indicate that out of all five pragmatic elements, the topic of deictic expressions proved to be the most familiar for this group. Therefore, the score gain in this particular category ranks as the highest among other pragmatic strategies (1.34). Conversely, in the individual group, the topic of English presupposition is considered to be the most challenging topic for its members. As a result, their score gain on presupposition is very low (0.17). This indicates English speech acts are the most problematic for this individual group. It could be affirmed that the individual Telegram activities significantly contribute to the score enhancement in the categories of English implicature and deictic expressions.

Table 5: Summary of independent t-test results

Assumption	Levene's test					
	F	Sig	T	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Score	Mean Difference
Equal variances assumed	2.64	0.107	5.019	0.000	64.25	11.49
Equal variances not assumed			5.048	0.000	52.76	11.49

According to the statistical analysis shown in Table 5, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis H_0 (p -value < 0.05), and thus the alternative hypothesis H_a is accepted. It could be explained that there was a significant difference between the pragmatics test results of learners who were taught

collaboratively using Telegram group activities compared to the pragmatics scores attained by learners who were taught using individual ones.

4. Discussion:

The present study attempted to make a comparison between the effects on Iraqi EFL learners taught using the collaborative Telegram model and the individual Telegram model (both adopting the virtual classroom model) in activities to develop pragmatic competence. The results reveal that the Iraqi EFL learners who were taught video materials on pragmatic activities using the collaborative Telegram model achieved significantly higher scores than those using the individual Telegram model. The results also show that Iraqi EFL learners' post-test scores for pragmatic communicative skills within the collaborative Telegram groups are statistically higher than their pre-test scores. The results of the study provide different understandings toward the implementation of the virtual classroom wherein the traditional approach video discussion and task activities carried out outside the classroom are accomplished through face-to-face discussion.

However, one of the possible limitations is that when one of the learners cannot attend the face-to-face discussion model because of external or non-academic factors such as illness, inclement weather, or even limited time for the discussion meeting, the virtual classroom model will be far from optimal. Consequently, based on this study, by combining the virtual classroom approach using the Telegram application, learners can discuss the video through their Telegram group without any boundaries or obstacles.

Telegram collaborative instruction is viewed to be highly advantageous because of its vital merits. This result agrees with Suranakkharin's (2017) empirical study in which the Thai EFL learners' ability in mastering collocations was significantly advanced after the implementation of the virtual classroom model. With the application of a virtual model of teaching pragmatics using Telegram in the current study, it should be affirmed that Telegram can eliminate boundaries between students and their teachers and motivate collaborative learning activities. Moreover, even autonomous learning can be enhanced and developed by implementing Telegram mobile application in the process of teaching pragmatic competence. This recalls Alzubi and Singh's (2018) study in which they examined the influence of social strategies employing smartphones on EFL Saudi learners' autonomous abilities and skills in reading skills. Their findings convey that the use of smartphone applications endorses EFL learners' reading skill autonomy.

In line with previous studies such as Raja & Saeed (2012) and Hazea & Alzubi (2016), collaborative learning, the flexibility of the virtual classroom model, and Telegram have been seen as a foundation for the development of pragmatic competence. Such a model and technology allow EFL learners to envision the concept of pragmatics by way of videos through their Telegram including speech acts, implicature, politeness, deictic expressions, and presupposition, that lead to more flexible, effective, dynamic and interactive virtual classroom group activities. Accordingly, this reinforces high pragmatic competency on a part of Iraqi EFL learners.

As for collaborative learning, it seems that the small group Telegram virtual approach in teaching pragmatic strategies has a positive effect on learning about pragmatic competence. This result matches the results of Muslem et al. (2017) and Arifani (2019) in their study of small group and individual learning models. These studies claim that small group collaborative learning activities have a positive effect on the speaking performance and skills of EFL learners. However, it is still stimulating to determine exactly to what extent the impact of collaborative learning in small groupings is, and whether it directly affects the learners' mastery of pragmatic strategies in general.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations:

This research was conducted to compare whether the learners taught by virtual classroom involving small groups via Telegram with pragmatics-related activities carried out by small groups was found out to be more effective in the enhancement of pragmatic competence with regard to speech act strategies, politeness, implicature, deictic expressions, and presupposition. Generally, the findings indicated that learners' scores for pragmatic strategies improved significantly. The results also demonstrated that learners who were instructed implementing the virtual classroom model involving small groups via Telegram achieved better than those taught utilizing the individual virtual grouping via Telegram. It is recommended that the teachers of pragmatics and communicative skills should employ the amalgamation of the collaborative group-based virtual classroom model and Telegram as a supportive learning tool through small group activity models in the teaching and learning process and should implement this combination with their EFL curriculum. Thus, further research to better comprehend one of the aforementioned pragmatic notions would be worth conducting.

6. Declaration of Competing Interest:

None

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9. References:

1. AbdAlfattah, S. (2015). The effectiveness of using a WhatsApp messenger as one of mobile learning technique to develop students' writing skills. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6, 32-45.
2. Akçayır, G., & Akçayır, M. (2018). The flipped classroom: A review of its advantages and challenges. *Computers Education*, 126 (1), 334-345. [10.1016/j.compedu.2018.07.021](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.07.021).
3. Alfaki, I., & Alharthy, K. (2014). Towards a digital world: Using social networks to promote learner's language. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 4(10), 105-114.
4. Alzubi, A. A. F., & Singh, M. K. (2018). The impact of social strategies through smartphones on the Saudi learners' socio-cultural autonomy in EF1 reading context. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 11(1), 31-40.
5. Amaya, I. (2008). Teaching culture: is it possible to avoid pragmatic failure?. *Revista Alicantina de Estudios Ingleses*, 21, 11-24.
6. Arifani, Y. (2019). The application of small WhatsApp groups and the individual flipped instruction model to boost EF1 learners' mastery of collocation. *CA11-EJ*, 20(1), 52-73.
7. Arifani, Y., Asari, S., Anwar, K. & Budianto, I. (2019). Individual or collaborative WhatsApp learning? A flipped classroom model of EF1 writing instruction. *Teaching English with Technology*, 20(1), 122-139.
8. Bachman, I. (1990). *Fundamental considerations in language testing*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
9. Białystok, E. (1993). Symbolic representation and attentional control in pragmatic competence. In Kasper, G., & Blum-Kulka, S. (Eds.) *Interlanguage Pragmatics* (pp: 43-57). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
10. Byram, M. (1995). *Intercultural competence and mobility in multinational contexts: A European vision*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.
11. Canale, M. (1988). The measurement of communicative competence. *Annual review of applied linguistics*, 8, 67-84.
12. Canale, M., & Swain, M. (1980). Theoretical bases of communicative approach to second language teaching and testing. *Applied linguistics*, 1, 1-47.
13. Chik, A., & Ho, J. (2017). Learn a language for free: Recreational learning among adults. *System*, 69, 162-171.
14. Chomsky, N. (1980). *Rules and representations*. New York: Columbia University Press.
15. Hamdan, N., McKnight, P., McKnight, K., & Arfstrom, K. M. (2013). *The flipped learning model: A white paper based on the literature review titled "A Review of Flipped Learning."* Arlington, VA: Flipped Learning Network.
16. Hazea, A. N., & Alzubi, A. A. (2016). The effectiveness of using mobile on EF1 learners' reading practices in Najran University. *English Language Teaching*, 9(5), 8-21.
17. Hymes, D. (1964). On communicative competence. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press. In C.J. Brumfit & K. Johnson (Eds.) (1979), *The communicative approach to language teaching* (pp: 5-26). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
18. Kabooha, R. & Elyas, T. (2018). The effects of Youtube in multimedia instruction for vocabulary learning: perceptions of EF1 students and teachers. *English Language Teaching*, 11 (2), 72-81.
19. Kasper, G. (2001). Classroom research on interlanguage pragmatics. In Kasper, G., & Rose, K. (Eds.). *Pragmatics and language teaching*, (pp.33-60). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
20. Khoshsiman, H., Toroujeni, S. M. H., & Samani, F. S. (2017). The impact of digital item presentation on the intermediate level language learners' testing performance and attitudes towards onscreen test in private language learning context. *Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Research*, 4(3), 196-211.
21. Krisnawati, E. (2011). Pragmatic competence in the spoken English classrooms. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 1 (1).105-115.
22. Lankshear, C., & Knobel, M. (2006). *New literacies: Everyday Practices and Classroom Learning* (2nd ed.). Maidenhead: Open University Press.
23. Leech, G. (1990). *Principles of pragmatics*. New York: Longman.
24. Levinson, S. C. (1983). *Pragmatics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
25. Meier, A.J. (1992). *A sociopragmatic contrastive study of repair work in Austrian German and American English*. Unpublished Ph.D. dissertation, University of Vienna.
26. Motteram, G. (2013). *Innovations in learning technologies for English language teaching*. London: British Council.
27. Mrowa-Hopkins, C. & Strambi, A. (2005). How angry can you be in French and Italian? Integrating research and teaching for the development of pragmatic competence in 12 classrooms. *Flinders University Languages Group Online Review*, 2(2), 48-62.

29. Muslem, A., Mustafa, F., Usman, B., & Rahman, A. (2017). The application of video clips with small group and individual activities to improve young learners' speaking performance. *Teaching English with Technology*, 17(4), 25-37.
30. Muzhir, H. D, Raheem, M., Ghani, A. (2013). The role of video conferencing in the development of pragmatic competence in Iraqi EF1 university classes. *The Internet Journal of Language, Culture and Society*, 38, 57-68.
31. Nobre, Ana Maria de Jesus Ferreira (2018). Multimedia technologies and online task-based foreign language teaching-learning. *Tuning Journal for Higher Education*, 5(2), 75-97.
32. Raja, N., & Saeed, A. (2012). The effectiveness of group work and pair work for students of English at undergraduate level in public and private sector colleges. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 4(5), 155-163.
33. Reinhardt, J. (2019). Social media in second and foreign language teaching and learning: Blogs, wikis, and social networking. *Language Teaching*, 52(1), 1-39.
34. Rostami, F., & Khodabandeh, F., (2019). A comparative study of language style variations in e-mail and Telegram messages by non-native intermediate learners of English. *Teaching English with Technology*, 19(4), 69-89.
35. Sales, N. (2013). Flipped the classroom: Revolutionising legal research training. *Legal Information Management*, 13(4), 231-235.
36. Schmidt, R. (1993) "Consciousness, learning and interlanguage pragmatics". In G. Kasper and S. Blum-Kulka (Eds.). *Interlanguage Pragmatics*, (pp. 21-43). New York: Oxford University Press.
37. Shirkhani, S., (2014). Technology-enhanced teaching of pragmatic competence. *I-manager's Journal on English Language Teaching*, 4(3), 1-8.
38. Suranakkharin, T. (2017). Using the flipped model to foster Thai learners' second language collocation knowledge. *31: The Southeast Asian Journal of English Language Studies*, 23(3), 1-20.
39. Sykes, J.M. (2005). Synchronous chat and pragmatic development: Effects of oral and written chat. *CAIICO Journal*, 22, 399-431.
40. Warschauer, M. & Grimes, D. (2007). Audience, authorship, and artifact: The emergent semiotics of Web 2.0. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 27, 1-23.
41. Zhu, Y., & Chen, H. (2015). Social media and human need satisfaction: Implications for social media marketing. *Business Horizons*, 58, 335-345.